

PERLITE AS A MICROBIAL CARRIER: A BIOREMEDIATION SOLUTION FOR MARINE OIL-SPILLS

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ABSTRACT

Over the last five decades, nearly 6 million tons of oil have contaminated our oceans solely from tanker spills, according to Ritchie et al., 2022, posing severe environmental and economic risks. Despite the development of various methods to contain oil spills, even advanced technologies have limitations associated with environmental and economic factors. Conventional cleanup methods face limitations, such as smoke production from in situ burning and dependency on calm seas for booms and skimmers. Oil absorption using industrial minerals, like perlite or bentonite, although cost-effective still poses challenges regarding collection and treatment of the remaining product and byproducts. The proposed innovative solution integrates perlite absorption with bioremediation methods, by utilizing an inorganic carrier acting as a “living sponge”, hosting oil-degrading microorganisms. Perlite’s lightweight and buoyant nature, enhanced by bioremediation functionalities, allows it to float on water and facilitate easy deployment, making it reliable for immediate oil spill response, resulting in non-toxic residues, while supporting global sustainability goals by preserving marine ecosystems and promoting economic competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Tanker spill failures occupy 45% of total ocean oil pollution, while over the last decade the estimated oil amount of marine oil-spills are almost reaching 4 billion liters in the oceans. These massive amounts of oil-spills, apart from industrial disasters, are also a result of the advanced needs for oil exploitation and thus increased needs for extraction and transport leading to increased incident risks. The main pollutants of the oil-spill content are saturated and aromatic hydrocarbons from the various distillation residues of crude oil being light crude, heavy crude and bitumen. Although several other toxic components exist in relatively small concentrations, they are often mistakenly not taken into consideration. These components are natural gasses and potentially toxic elements (PTEs), like saturated hydrocarbons with sulfur, oxygen and nitrogen contents and even smaller concentrations of metals like nickel, palladium, arsenic and copper. The toxic components of crude oil and byproducts disrupt marine ecosystems and even cause mortality of marine and

coastal organisms affecting the biodiversity of these environments. Marine oil spills are also causing severe socio-economic problems apart from environmental problems. After major oil-spill incidents, the social acceptance has decreased regarding exploration, extraction and transport of oil from people living in coastal areas and not only. Also, it causes major problems at the economy of countries that are based on tourism and simultaneously face these problems [1]. However, the existence of oil in these environments is not the only concerning parameter of this form of destruction, as the current remediation systems also pose significant dangers for the environment. Current solutions like booms and skimmers, in-situ burning and chemical dispersants either emit significantly large amounts of GreenHouse Gasses (GHG), are unable to gather the needed amount of pollutant from the ocean or leave other residue causing a new cycle of negative impactful reactions to happen [2], [3].

In the current study a new, adaptable and simplified technology addressing oil spills is proposed, wherein perlite, an industrial mineral, acts as a “living sponge” hosting oil degrading microorganisms. This aims to utilize the functionalities of industrial minerals such as porosity and high specific surface area, to absorb nutrients and immobilize oil-degrading bacteria in-situ, facilitating the consumption of oil [4]. Notably, the residue remaining after the bioremediation process is non-toxic to marine ecosystems [5], supporting contemporary goals of global environmental sustainability while also promoting economic competitiveness in the realm of sustainability [6].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Current Methods for Combating Oil Spills

The most common and currently used remediation techniques for treating marine oil spills are quite effective, however they have several economic and environmental sustainability disadvantages.

Booms And Skimmers

Booms are deployed to contain the spread of oil and facilitate its collection for easier recovery. Skimmers, on the other hand, are designed to remove oil from the water's surface. They typically include a recovery component, such as a flotation device or a support and transfer system, like a pump, which is used to transfer the collected oil and water into storage tanks [7]. The mechanical recovery of oil from marine environments is frequently used to combat large oil spills (>700 tonnes), but it is expensive, complex, and labor-intensive. It requires large ships, trained responders, extensive containment booms, skimming systems, pumping equipment, temporary storage, and disposal systems. Mechanical recovery rarely exceeds a 20% efficiency rate and is highly dependent on wind speed, becoming ineffective when winds exceed one or two knots. Additionally, the recovered mix of oil, water, and debris requires further processing and incineration, adding to costs [3].

In-situ Burning

In contrast, in-situ burning is a low-cost, simple, and quick method requiring minimal specialized equipment and personnel. It essentially involves the controlled burning of oil, with its efficiency exceeding 95%. However, it poses significant environmental risks, including the potential for secondary fires that threaten human life, property, and resources. In-situ burning is often avoided in marshland environments due to the risk of permanent plant damage from high ignition temperatures. Other limiting factors include oil type, weathering, emulsification, and environmental conditions. Concerns over atmospheric emissions, including carbon dioxide, water vapor, soot, carbon monoxide, and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), also hinder widespread acceptance [2], [3].

Chemical Dispersants

Chemical dispersants, when properly applied, can treat relatively large quantities of oil at much faster rates than mechanical recovery, thereby removing the oil from the water's surface and dispersing it into the water column, significantly reducing its environmental impact. However, there are two main issues associated with their use. Firstly, they offer only a temporary solution, as they do not completely remove the oil from the water but merely transfer it from the surface to the column. Secondly, the use of dispersants involves a trade-off between the toxicity to aquatic life and the benefits of protecting birds and mammals and preventing oil from reaching the shoreline. The primary concern is their toxicity to the larval and egg stages of marine fisheries. Generally, dispersants are an expensive, complex, and labor-intensive remediation method that requires special permission in most countries for their application [3].

Sorbents

For small-scale oil spills, sorbents are effective agents for removing oil from the water. Sorbents operate through two primary mechanisms: absorption and adsorption. Absorption involves the penetration of liquids into the porous spaces of the material, while adsorption entails the accumulation of liquids onto the surface of the material without penetration [8], [9]. The most commonly used sorbents are industrial minerals such as perlite and bentonite, which are notably inexpensive. Specifically, the average cost of one ton of perlite in 2023 was approximately \$67 [10], while the price of bentonite per ton was around \$99 [11], making these materials economically viable. This method boasts a low capital cost due to the affordability of these industrial minerals and is also relatively straightforward to apply. Laboratory tests conducted by Teas et al. using three different particle sizes of perlite demonstrated a recovery rate of up to 70%, effectively absorbing nearly 70% of the original oil present in the water. However, the overall cost of the method increases significantly due to the need to collect and further process the oil-soaked sorbent. The collection of residues can become particularly challenging under adverse sea conditions, such as high winds and strong tides. Despite its initial low cost and environmental friendliness, the technique can incur high costs due to the complexities of collecting and processing the mixture of oil, water, and industrial minerals [12].

Case Studies

Over the past 50 years, tanker spills alone have resulted in nearly 6 million tons of oil contaminating our oceans [13]. In major incidents involving the spill of more than 50,000 tons of

oil, the aforementioned techniques were employed, revealing significant drawbacks. For instance, in 1978, the Amoco Cadiz incident off the coast of Brittany, France, released 230,000 tons of light crude oil into the marine environment, polluting nearly 300 km of coastline. Both booms and skimmers and in-situ burning techniques were applied, ultimately costing approximately \$282 million. This spill resulted in the death of over 3,450 seabirds and severely affected fisheries, oyster beds, and seaweed habitats [14], [15].

Eleven years later, in 1989, the infamous Exxon Valdez disaster occurred in Prince William Sound, Alaska. This tragic event released over 340,000 tons of oil into the sea, contaminating 1,900 km of coastline. The primary response techniques included booms and skimmers, which demonstrated low recovery rates. Sorbents were also employed in situations where mechanical recovery was considered impractical. However, they were quickly dismissed due to the generation of additional solid waste, which necessitated labor-intensive collection efforts. Additionally, in-situ burning initially appeared effective but quickly became ineffective due to the changing state of the oil. The total cleanup cost was estimated at approximately \$2.1 billion, making it the most expensive cleanup effort at that time. The spill resulted in the deaths of 250,000 seabirds, 2,800 sea otters, 250 bald eagles, and 22 killer whales [14], [7], [15].

In 1990, during the Gulf War, over 650 oil wells in Kuwait were set ablaze, resulting in the spill of nearly 1 million tons of oil. Due to the ongoing conflict, no significant efforts were made to recover this vast amount of oil, leading to the deaths of more than 20,000 seabirds [14], [15].

One of the more recent large oil spills is that of the Deepwater Horizon incident. The latter serves as a compelling case study to highlight the necessity of innovative oil spill remediation technologies. In 2010, approximately 700,000 tons of crude oil were discharged into the Gulf of Mexico [13], covering an estimated 149,000 square kilometers of marine surface. The spill lasted for 87 days, and the subsequent cleanup efforts extended over several years. During the 87-day cleanup, the operation involved 2 drilling ships, 835 skimmers, and approximately 9,000 vessels on the most demanding day, over 6,000 vessels, 82 helicopters, and 47,849 personnel were deployed. Additionally, 3,795,985 feet of containment booms were used. In-situ burning was employed, with a total of 411 in-situ burns that removed an estimated 250,000 barrels of oil. A total of 68,530 gallons (1,632 barrels) of dispersant was applied. The total cost of the cleanup operations was staggering, estimated at around \$14 billion [16].

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Compared to the existing solutions, the proposed methodology of loaded perlite with degrading microorganisms is a sustainable bio-based approach, utilizing natural ingredients aligned with the current sustainability goals. The primary components of this method are perlite, which is an inorganic mineral, and a consortium of naturally occurring hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria, both of which are environmentally benign throughout the application. The production steps of the proposed solution are easy to follow and so is the application. First comes the preprocessing of perlite-carrier in order to create the conditions for maximum active surface for the microorganisms to be embedded. Then follows the preparation of the selected microbial consortium by providing nutrients and incubating the mixture and lastly the preparation of the final mixture that requires the addition of the microorganisms to the carrier. A wide portfolio of indigenous bacteria can be

applied, capable of efficiently degrading oil in the local environmental conditions [4]. The selection of activated perlite as the carrier and the base of this biotechnology twinning is done after considering perlite's high sorption capacity, its low cost and its relatively low environmental impact, thus being characterized as one of the top minerals used as sorbents [17]

Figure 1: Production flow chart

Production Process and Bio-based Components

Preparation Of Carrier

The processing starts with the extraction of the raw perlite ore from the quarry. The extracted perlite is then transported to a processing plant for further refinement, in order to minimize the transportation, cost the processing can be executed onsite. Firstly, the raw perlite ore is crushed so that a uniform size is achieved, then the pulverized ore passes through a temperature-regulated rotary kiln dryer to eliminate surplus moisture. It is of the utmost importance to control the temperature during the drying process in order to avoid overheating the perlite particles and thus preserve the ore's properties for expansion. After the drying process is complete the now dehydrated perlite is processed through a series of screens with progressively smaller openings, as a result, it is grouped into different sizes. The succeeding and final process is that of the expansion which unlocks the full potential of the perlite mineral. It should be noted that the sorted raw perlite may require further transfer to specialized facilities, which are equipped with the necessary high-temperature furnaces that are needed for the expansion procedure. These furnaces, oriented vertically, subject the raw perlite to intense heat ranging from 900-1000°C, it is noteworthy that conveyors and elevator systems control the feed rate of the furnace. The balance of heat and air flow within the furnace causes the expansion of the raw perlite. Finally, the newly formed expanded perlite particles undergo air cyclone classification for cooling and sorting and once again screens further refine the particles into their final grades, ensuring uniformity [4].

Microbial preparation

The perlite carrier can accommodate a plethora of microorganisms for ensuring high effectiveness levels and environmental conditions restoration. Based on the suitable oil-eating bacteria, their

effectiveness levels, the environmental conditions of the polluted area and the composition of the pollutant, the right selection of microorganisms affects the result of biodegradation. The needed amount of microorganism's consortium is added to an incubator with nutrients, covering their needs for phosphorus and nitrogen and sterilized seawater for the bacterial incubation and preparation for embedding to the carrier to start [18]. Focusing on bacteria, due to their high efficiency levels, even though depending on the available microorganisms of the area algae, yeast and fungi can be supplementarily used, the *Table I* shows some of the available microorganisms that are globally found, easy to survive in various environments and highly effective for the required conditions. Most of the times the coexistence of various microorganisms gives off better living conditions to the system and thus longevity and better results [5], [19].

Table 1: Globally available and abundant oil-eating bacteria for biodegradation [5], [19]

Microorganisms	Habitat	Pollutant	Sensitivity	Strength	Degradation efficiency (6-16 days)
Bacteria					
Pseudomonas spp.	Marine, river, soil	n-alkanes	Dependent in the pH and temperature condition	Can degrade a wide range of hydrocarbons	Up to 95%
Rhodococcus sp.	Marine, river, soil	Hexadecane	Nutrient requirements and slow growth rate	Can survive in high salinity and low temperature conditions	Up to 84%
Halomonas sp.	Marine, river, soil	Diesel fuel	Sensitive to temperature fluctuations	Survives in high salinity and high temperature conditions	Up to 50%
Alcanivorax borkumensis	Marine, river, soil	Hexadecane, BTEX	Sensitive to nutrient availability	Common in marine oil spills	Up to 82%
Thalassolituus oleivorans	Marine	Phenanthrene, pyrene	Does not work well with other oil-eating bacteria	Adapts well to marine conditions, thus ideal for in-situ	Up to 70%
Algae					
Chlorella vulgaris	Marine	Crude oil	Sensitive to nutrient availability	Enhances the aerobic degradation of other microorganisms	Up to 94.3

Microbial Embedding

After the preparation of both the carrier and microorganisms is complete, the expanded perlite is then embedded with the oil-degrading bacteria. Firstly, the nutrient solution used for microbial preparation is integrated into the carrier using a screw mixer in order to be absorbed into the processed perlite's high surface area, acting as a food source before the oil-bacteria-interaction that will provide the microorganisms with carbon. This allows immobilization of the microorganisms on the nutrient layer, enabling them to colonize the perlite's pores. The perlite, inoculated with a hydrocarbon clastic bacterial consortium is then freeze-dried to preserve the bacterial cells and extend the product's shelf life. At this point the production is complete, and the product is applied to the oil spill area, followed by the eventual biodegradation of the absorbed oil. The degradation process typically takes 14 days to achieve an excellent 93% degradation degree

[2]. The bacteria are then bioconverted into environmentally friendly biomass, thereby reducing disruption of the marine ecosystem's food chain and protecting marine biodiversity. Meanwhile, the perlite particles float harmlessly, posing no threats, allowing its potential collection and reuse, thus promoting circular economy [4].

Figure 2: Visualization of biotechnology twining

Application Process and Remaining Residue

The application of the produced sorbent onto the marine oil-spill is based on a simple process that can have several differentiations, following the portfolio of solutions approach that was mentioned, depending on multiple parameters. The main parameters that affect the selection of on the one hand the microorganisms but on the other hand the application method, are mainly the toxic components of the to-be-treated oil spill, the amount of oil, but also the location of the oil spill and the environmental conditions of the area [17]

In the first and simplest approach, the material can be directly applied to the polluted site and left in the marine environment for the remaining time of biodegradation and after that is complete. That leads to no required post-processing since the carrier is a non-toxic industrial mineral and the remaining biomass consists of microorganisms, mainly bacteria, that already exist in marine environments and have already consumed most of the oil content [5] The elimination of post-processing with an environmentally friendly residue not only brings the cost of the process down but it also decreases the environmental impact of the remediation [6].

Figure 3: Process and application flow chart

On the other hand, the approach that fits the circular economy framework requires booms that will prevent the oil from spreading in order to gather the material after the oil has been absorbed. After the recovery of the oil-absorbed carrier, the biodegradation of oil can be completed on the way to the processing site and so the removal of oil from the marine environment is completed in less time [6]. The post-process of the material depends on the further utilization of the carrier with some of the proposed usages to be mentioned in section 4.3. One more point in order for the idea to be holistically in the circular economy framework, is the implementation of the reuse/repurposing of perlite from other applications similar to the proposed, with one example is the repurposing of perlite pesticides into the perlite carrier [20].

Figure 4: Visualization of the proposed application method that fits the circular economy framework

DISCUSSION

Advantages Of the Proposed Solution

The microbial carrier technology proposed for oil spill combat offers several benefits, significantly reducing the ecological footprint of remediation efforts. Specifically, it is aligned with various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), set by the United Nations to create a sustainable framework for future development. According to the 2024 progress report, only 17% of SDGs are on track. The assessment shows significant deviations from the 2030 agenda, with half of the goals making minimal to moderate progress, while the rest are stalled or regressed. This technology focuses on SDGs 8, 13, and 14. Progress on G13 is minimal while G8 and G14 have only reached 10% of their targets, as shown in table 2 below [21].

Table 2: Progress table of referred SDGs [21]

SDG	Goal Description	Progress (%)		
		On Track	Minimal Progress	Stagnation or Regression
G8	Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all	10	40	50
G13	Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts	0	70	30
G14	Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development	10	50	40

The data provided highlight the need for further development to reach these goals. In particular, the proposed technology is aligned with G8.8, ensuring a safe working environment, minimizing risks, and addressing formal employment (G8.3 and G8.5), with an indirect impact on tourism (G8.9).

Environmental Advantages

On the environmental side, G13.2 highlights the dangerous rise in global temperatures caused by greenhouse gasses, despite reduction efforts by developed countries, while G14.3 indicated a concerning increase in ocean acidification due to rising CO₂ emissions. The application and degradation process of the proposed methodology is environmentally friendly and efficient, while post-degradation, the remaining perlite and biomass are non-toxic. While extensive use of the in-situ burning method will result in both high emissions and severe acidification of the oceans, the microbial carrier ensures minimal carbon footprint.

The inexpensive raw materials together with the benign nature of the remains after remediation, which eliminate the need for additional treatments or disposal processes, make the proposed solution an economically sustainable option for oil spill remediation. The cost-effectiveness and easy application can also be adapted to developing countries, facing severe oil contamination due to increased “marine traffic” and shifts in global crude oil trade patterns, resulting from the ongoing war [22]. This also results in their contribution to reducing greenhouse gasses by not using inexpensive conventional methods.

Apart from the direct impact the microbial carrier has on the aforementioned SDGs, the technology also has an indirect influence on goals 1, 3, 6 and 9 [21].

Technical Advantages

On the technical side, the microbial carrier shows excellent features, including versatility. It is adaptable to various marine and climatic conditions, overcoming limitations faced by conventional

methods. The perlite-based carrier can be deployed quickly and effectively, regardless of sea state, making it a reliable option for immediate response to oil spills [17].

Economic Advantages

Finally, on the economical side, according to the Mineral Commodity Summaries 2024, Greece holds 22% of the world's perlite production, being the third producer globally. Although China is the leading producer, most of the perlite is consumed internally, while Greece and Turkey are leading exporters. This data ensures enhanced competitiveness for Greece as the main component of the product is perlite, supporting the market, while innovation and production remains internal [10].

Comparison With Existing Methods

Conventional methods for oil spill cleanup often prove inefficient or come with direct or indirect environmental impacts. For instance, mechanical recovery rarely exceeds a 20% efficiency rate and is highly dependent on wind conditions [3]. In-situ burning, is highly effective with a 95% efficiency rate but introduces significant risks, including the potential for secondary fires, irreversible damage to vegetation and the release of harmful emissions like carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide and polyaromatic hydrocarbons [2], [3]. Chemical dispersants also increase toxicity to aquatic life, are expensive to use and labor-intensive [3].

On the other hand, using inorganic minerals as sorbents offers a 70% efficiency rate and is environmentally benign due to the nature of the minerals. Bentonite and Perlite that are commonly used are inexpensive, but the overall cost of the technique can be high due to the need to collect and process the resulting mixture of oil, water and minerals [12]. The proposed technology offers a more effective, eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to the mineral sorbents. Primarily, the breakdown of oil hydrocarbons into non-toxic components eliminates the need for post-processing, thereby reducing the cost and minimizing ecological disruption. Furthermore, perlite's lightweight and buoyant nature facilitates easy deployment and remediation, as it floats with the absorbed oil regardless of sea conditions [17], making it effective in various sea states, unlike booms and skimmers. Even if the material disperses, the microorganisms loaded onto it can continue consuming the absorbed oil within perlite's pores, as a result of the protected environment provided by the carrier.

CONCLUSION

In summary conventional oil spill remediation methods have several drawbacks. Mechanical recovery is environmentally friendly but inefficient, while in-situ burning and chemical dispersants are highly efficient but environmentally harmful. Inorganic minerals as sorbents need post-processing. The perlite carrier binded with oleophilic microorganisms shows promising performance regarding the degradation of oil in marine environments and easy deployment. The microbial carrier proposed, combines the advantages of the traditional methods, offering an environmentally sustainable process with a high efficiency, by integrating the capability of absorption and adsorption that inorganic minerals have and microbial bioremediation. While

promoting the use of natural materials, this approach supports the broader objective of preserving marine biodiversity and protecting coastal ecosystems.

Recommendations For Future Research

Environmental problems of our times have created opportunities for technology to go even further while making mindful decisions for the future generations. On the circular economy approach of this proposed material, the reuse of the remaining perlite carrier fits as a part of a solution of a major environmental problem, that being global warming. The recovery of the perlite-carrier and the embedding of algae can be implemented at a carbon capturing project for industrial carbon dioxide emissions. Perlite is an absorbent that can absorb atmospheric carbon dioxide more than ½ times its weight and it has been used as a sustainable catalytic component [23], [24]. Algae on the other hand, has the ability to capture significant amounts of carbon dioxide around 1.8 times its produced biomass weight, especially the proposed species *Chlorella* spp. of this paper that has been characterized as the best species for industrial emissions capture [25]. Focusing on the base of this proposed idea but not being limited to that, soil remediation can also be another outlook of the possible reuse for environmental solutions, following the perlite-based fertilizer approach that has had positive outcomes [20].

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

Methodology, M.-S.F.; I.P.; and D.P. Validation, A.P.; Investigation, M.-S.F.; I.P.; and D.P.; Resources, M.-S.F.; I.P.; and D.P.; Writing—original draft preparation, M.-S.F.; I.P.; and D.P.; Writing—review and editing, M.-S.F.; I.P.; and D.P.; Supervision, A.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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